

5G INTELLIGENT AUTOMOTIVE NETWORK APPLICATIONS

A Horizon 2020 project that will provide an open 5G experimentation platform to enable the development, deployment and testing of Automotive related 5G applications

5G-IANA will

- Create new business opportunities and boost market for start-ups and SMEs with Automotive NetApps
- Increase road safety and reduce automobile carbon footprint by leveraging Connected and Automated Mobility using enhanced network performances
- Implement and trial Connected and Automated Driving relevant Use Cases to validate and assess the AOEP (Automotive Open Experimental Platform) suitability and functional improvements
- Provide accurate localization and low latency mission-critical applications
- Specify and provide the 5G-IANA AOEP
- Specify and implement a repository environment for NetApps and VNFs to ease the design and chaining of new automotive-related services

Test Beds

NOKIA testbed
in **Ulm** (Germany)

TELEKOM SLOVENIJE (TS)
in **Ljubljana** (Slovenia)

5G-IANA will be demonstrated through **seven automotive-related use cases** in two 5G testbeds

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The 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership

Partners

General project info

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€ 7.649.795

EU contribution
€ 5.999.969

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Coordinated by:

ICCS (Greece)

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